

Impact of Team Effectiveness, Affective Commitment, Opportunity, Fair Treatment, and Job Involvement on Participative Leadership

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of participative leadership on team performance, affective commitment, opportunity, fair treatment, and job involvement. The path-goal theory is discussed in this work as a hypothetical viewpoint that demonstrates how the hypothesis has been improved. For this action, a quantitative method was used. 250 questionnaires were distributed in Karachi's manufacturing sector. For the test investigation, a sample size of 201 was used. The results of the test analysis, which was conducted using SPSS software, show how participative leadership is influenced by team effectiveness, affective commitment, opportunity, fairness, and job involvement. The study found a strong correlation between participative leadership and team effectiveness, affective commitment, and fair treatment. While there is little correlation between opportunities and job involvement with participatory leadership.

Keywords: Participative Leadership, Team Effectiveness, Affective Commitment, Opportunity, Fair Treatment, Job Involvement

1. Introduction

In today's time, participative leadership is considered to be linked with the motivation and improvement of organizational commitment. It always inspires the workers to take an active part in making decisions which results in enhancement in their working live (Ardekani & Jahromi, 2011). Employee observes high inducement level because of the leader as well as their need for the attainment of ideas sharing and performing their jobs in a good way (Fatima, Safder, & Jahanzab, 2017). Leadership is an energetic process in which there is a chain of roles. To give importance to employee performance they should also do efforts to improve communication so that workers shall be aware of changes made in a firm (Mollo, Stanz, & Groenewald, 2005). In several past studies, participative leadership has been found beneficial in shaping employee performance (Hwang et al., 2015). This research shows a relationship among participative leadership, job involvement, opportunities, fair treatment, team effectiveness & commitment. We have focused on participative leadership because it is like joint decision-making between a manager and a subordinate (Newman, Herman, & Schwarz, 2018). Establishing the new policies will come to directive leadership but apply for the idea would enhance the high performance of workers. Inspiration, reliability & empathy are the features of successful leaders. It identifies that the leadership style used here will increase the level of satisfaction among employees & when the worker is happy with job responsibilities so his/her performance automatically enhances. It will increase the high level of motivation level and improve the effectiveness of particular organizations and employees will not have job insecurity (Richter et al., 2018). Additionally, they investigated that association in the middle of occupation association & employment fulfillment. They also found that particular occupation contributions required a certain relationship for work fulfillment.

The effectiveness starts with the selection of a team it is the most important part to select the essential team. This shows the capabilities of finding exact skills as well as knowledge. When choosing the team leader must choose those people who will understand their vision & has different sets of qualities (Gadirajurrett et al., 2018). Affective commitment mainly builds up during work practice such as communications with administrators & working groups (Kim & Beehr, 2018). It refers to how much you are dedicated to the firm responsibilities. A willingness to give energy and time with the promise you have done with your company. An engagement is an alternate commitment that limits options for activity. It is accountability to do something actually what you have promised. It is considered that successful leadership required honesty delegation, hard work, and effective communication (Raziq et al., 2018).

Leaders should maintain a friendly environment with the workers to motivate them. Low leadership is arising due to the lack of communication, a decrease in motivation level, and dissatisfaction (Kouzes & Posner, 1997). They further elaborate that the fortunate leader caused a favorable level of commitment. The lack of effective leadership is a serious problem & being observed in many organizations. It is noticeable that the consequence is low performance, absenteeism of motivation, poor progress, and development of the firms. Therefore, this would sort to consider administration leadership style and organizational performance (Ukaidi, 2016). Enhancement of decision-making is vital for every organization. Participative leadership provides freedom for employees to be concerned and think about the betterment of the firm.

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With this deserving employees will be promoted for their creativity and loyalty to the organization (Moin, 2018). Leadership has become a problem in different sectors because it affects the opportunity for employees and the treatment which workers faced from leaders.

An autocratic leader always take decisions on his own he never tried to listen what are the employees' ideas. To investigate this problem of participative leadership is somehow the same as done in the industrial sector as we know that leadership is one of the important for the achievement of organizational goal (Ali et al., 2018). Leaders can use different style for accomplishment of goal. It is also identified that this approach is critical for the continuity of leadership procedures in long work environments. Employees are our human capital they should be treated like humans rather than machines (Subramony, Segers, & Chadwick, 2018).

2. Theoretical Framework and Development of Hypotheses

The Path goal theory (House, 1996) determined that a leader's nature must be backing and also an influence representative, such attitudes fulfill the subordinates' needs. In a participative style, the leader is permitted to the talent, and skill of each and every person required to achieve the best result. A leader is responsible for the final action but shares within a team to get more idea perception which makes this much more effective. The staff morale becomes very high while participating in the decision-making process. This will improve their workability and condition which is directly related to their workplace policies. Here retention takes place when your employees know that they will participate in future company growth and allow them to work with future circumstances. It is basically a managerial style that takes employee input while taking company decisions. The organization gave information about the issue they are having and use the voting technique (majority votes) in order to make a settlement.

It's another name is democratic leadership. Through this, we identify and resolve all problems through the ideas and perceptions of different people and fulfill firm goals and objectives. Normally many leaders believe in this style due to the involvement of their subordinates, through this employees feel respect in an organization which in turn makes them motivated and gives them inner happiness. When you work democratically with your team, means giving opportunities to your members the result will be creativity and hard work. Fair treatment is done when your supervisor or whom you're reporting treats you equally and unbiasedly. An equality base increases job satisfaction and retention. If we talk about opportunities, providing this to every staff member will develop their working style and their self-efficacy. Job involvement involves your members in a job they are doing and identified by.

2.1. Team Effectiveness & Participative Leadership

Participative leadership is defined as the process of the joint decision-making process between the leader and his workers (Benoliel & Somech, 2014). Using this strategy of leadership would be very critical to manage a team effectively (Newman et al., 2016). This shows the capabilities of finding exact skills as well as knowledge. When choosing the team leader must choose those people who will understand their vision & has different sets of qualities (Gadirajurrett et al., 2018). Team effectiveness is a vital dimension related to performance. It is basically a fundamental characteristic linked to individual work action. (Gadirajurrett et al., 2018). By enhancing team effectiveness, it will automatically improve their performance. Leadership is the capability to impact a group for the achievement of goals (Robbin, Judge, & Cambeli, 2010). Several studies identified that due to less attention and creativity, effectiveness is being slowed down and it is considered an important factor for effectiveness. Expecting more from the subordinate will result slowly in team effectiveness (Chen et al., 2018). According to (Yammarino & Yun, 2016) finding this engagement increases job tension & physiological burden. While experiencing this stress the members of the team will spend more and more time on finding solutions. The behavior of leaders impacts the structure, effectiveness & working process of a team (Hoch, 2013). It is found that participative leadership provides an advantage. This leadership enhances the group decision effectiveness due to the diverse knowledge which is related to career (Choi, Kim, & Kang, 2017).

Hypothesis 1: Team effectiveness has a significant impact on participative leadership

2.2. Affective Commitment & Participative Leadership

Commitment is more theoretical and empirical in the field of organizational behavior and human resources (Werang, 2017). Commitment is very important for every organization. Commitment has three dimensions 1) normative 2) affective 3) continuous. But in this research, one dimension i.e. affective is focused (Banjarnahor, 2016). Affective is self-awareness within the organization. If an employee is already aware of the organization their commitment will be high for the organization. It has a positive impact on the role of leadership performance. Affective is said to have a more powerful relation with it (Meyer, 1997). It has a positive impact on the commitment of the short tenure employee as they feel capable themselves for the organization (Huang et al., 2006). There are different ways why the employees leave the organization (Agapito et al., 2015). The main reason which is discovered was commitment (Tett & Meyer, 1993; Gartner, 1999; Du et al., 2006). Commitment is increased with the reward but it is decreased with the job cost

(Farrell & Rusbult, 1981). When the employee gets a reward for the performance his satisfaction level increases which leads him/her to the commitment.

Hypothesis 2: *Affective Commitment has a significant impact on Participative Leadership*

2.3. Opportunity & Participative Leadership

Opportunity given to employees basically gives them respect in order to participate in the decision-making. When an employee gets an opportunity his/her motivation level increases (Chamberlin, 2018). In participative leadership, leaders give opportunities to employees so that worker creativity and good ideas come to achieving organizational goals (Schmidt, 2010). Chance for workers to contribute satisfy their high-order requirements, such as self-expression & dependence, which helps the workers to experience more value from the leaders (Rock, 2009). This style provides the chance for the employee to utilize their right to be heard & be satisfied through their thoughts and participation. Workers enthusiastically concerned with the design, setting up & accomplish modify that have the chance to manipulate the result of the modification; it provides them with a good judgment of the organization & their control. Secondly, an interactive procedure throughout involvement generates the chance for expression of concern & the deliberation of effort, which will have an effect on the opinion of justice & the reaction of the person respected (Vandenbroucke, 2017).

Hypothesis 3: *Opportunity has a significant impact on Participative Leadership*

2.4. Fair Treatment & Participative Leadership

Being respectful is not just your benefit it will also benefit your surroundings. Respect for employees is the main key factor for every organization the employee are people who contribute to the problem-solving of the organization (Liker, 2003). It plays an important role in the generation and maintenance of effective organization (Rok, 2009). Every particular employee wants that their supervisor or upper management gives them respect, this makes them motivated and makes them committed to the firm. Respectful treatment for all the staff is one of the most important factors for the other. Motivation can make a huge level of empowerment (Kim, 2002). Employees' involvement and participation in the process of decision-making will increase their effectiveness (Luthans, 2002). It is considered the key variable that impacts the effectiveness of the organization. In highly competitive global business it's identified as the influence factor (Reddy & Sudneer, 2011). The employees performed more when they feel that they are rewarded fairly for the contribution they have done. (Fatt, Khin, & Heng, 2010).

Hypothesis 4: *Fair treatment has a significant impact on participative leadership*

2.5. Job Involvement & Participative Leadership

Job involvement has significant impact on individual self-image (Kanungo, 1982). A leader does not take all credit for success, they have to recognize the hard work of the team. (Liker, 2003; & Yukl, 2010) point out that participative leadership will go beyond for the sense and equality in the organization. Even though participative leaders engage workers in the processes of problem-solving & decision-making, they don't essentially present the definite role modeling & supervision which will support such human resources to be confident in their innovative capability (Miao, Newman, Schwarz, & Xu, 2013). Job involvement is basically a source that will decrease job demands, and helps the individual objective which is to accomplish goals & motivate personal development, with learning (Derk, 2018). Involvement is considered as the most efficient resource of management which is a key to organizational efficiency and work fulfillment (Stewart et al., 2011).

Hypothesis 5: *Job involvement has a significant impact on Participative Leadership*

3. Methodology

This research focused upon the Descriptive research. Methodology is an extensive theory of determining different techniques, methodical, hypothetical analysis methods for a field of study. These measures are used to find out the impact of team effectiveness, affective commitment, opportunity, fair treatment, and job involvement on participative leadership in the manufacturing industry of Karachi, Pakistan. Usually, it includes the concepts such as quantitative or qualitative, theoretical representation, and stage technology. In this section, the examination emphasizes on a brief summary about all the techniques & procedures which are used in this study for obtaining the results. The aim of this study is to see the relationship of the dependent variable that is participative leadership to see the impact among them with the help of explanatory technique is used. The data for this research has been gathered from the adopted questionnaire and based on the evaluation of the outcome through an investigative quantitative approach to transmit the outcome of the research. The collection of the data is formed by primary resources. The target audience has been gathered from the employees working in different organizations. This research is totally focused on the manufacturing industry. The technique for the survey is being used for data summary. Likert scale questionnaire is used for the data collection the item for participative leadership is taken from the empowering leadership ELQ, and fair treatment items are taken from (Niehoff & Moorman, 1993). Opportunity items are taken from Work Effectiveness CWEQ (Hatcher & Laschinger, 1996). Job involvement item is adapted from (Vroom, 1962) and team effectiveness is adopted through (Ancona & Caldwell, 1992). Lastly, Affective commitment is being taken from (Meyer, Barak, & Vandenberghe, 1996). For the current research, Karachi is being considered as a geographical location due to financial and time constraints. The target audience is both male and female, aged between 20-35 years. The target population of my research is the employees working in a team at different organizations. This research totally focused on the manufacturing industry. The non-probability sampling technique is used, as mentioned above that the data collection is taken from the manufacturing industry, and the purposive method research is done so on the basis of random sampling so that the respondent on the random basis will give a chance to share their valuable knowledge. In this study, SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) software is being used to evaluate the data. Multiple tests were applied including Regression as well as EFA. Reliability is also checked for the validation of data collected by the respondents.

3.1. Reliability Analysis using Cronbach Coefficient Alpha

The requirement for doing a pilot study is just to check whether the likert scale item was reliable and validated for the main study collection. 50 samples were collected for the pilot study. If the results show that the Likert items are reliable by checking the alpha value and Pearson correlation, then we will go forward with the main study. Reliability is an analysis that is done on spss for checking the item consistency. The value criteria according to (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016; Nunnally, 1978) for reliability is < 0.5 Poor 0.6 acceptable 0.7 good 0.8 excellent 0.9 marvelous

Table 1

Reliability(n= 50)		
Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Item
Team Effectiveness	0.791	7
Affective Commitment	0.711	6
Opportunity	0.667	7
Fair Treatment	0.714	7
Job Involvement	0.705	7
Participative Leadership	0.799	6

3.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis

The variables included were both dependent Participative Leadership with independent Team Effectiveness, Affective Commitment, Opportunity, Fair Treatment, and Job Involvement. For this research exploratory factor has been analyzed in order to the validity of Likert scale item. The test was run on 40 items out of which 17 were deducted & 23 Likert remained in the rotated matrix. The table indicated the rotated component matrix with its importance. Alpha variance explained percentage Eigen value & cumulative percentage explained is included in the table. If the value is greater than 0.5, it is considered good factor loading (Leech, 2007).KMO must be in excess of 0.70 for each indicator. The Bartlett test must be less than 0.05, which shows that the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix, which means one diagnosis should be off-diagonal (Leech, 2007). In this research, the value of KMO is .782 which is greater than

0.70, and 60.58% of total variance alphas α are 0.857 Participative Leadership, 0.764 Fair Treatment, 0.706 Job Involvement, 0.691 Team Effectiveness, 0.650 Affective Commitment and lastly 0.675 for Opportunity.

Table 2
KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.782
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1553.417
	Df	253
	Sig.	.000

Table 3

Exploratory Factor Analysis(n= 201)								
Indicators	Cronbach's Alpha	PL	FT	JI	TE	O	AC	Communalities
PL3		.835						.771
PL5		.798						.705
PL4	.857	.782						.666
PL2		.777						.676
PL1		.634						.538
FT1			.775					.644
FT2			.719					.581
FT3	.764		.709					.641
FT6			.676					.543
FT5			.553					.398
JI3				.789				.638
JI4				.745				.584
JI2	.706			.634				.574
JI1				.601				.463
JI6				.570				.434
TE2					.799			.682
TE1	.691				.735			.622
TE6					.561			.492
TE4					.552			.492
O5						.883		.806
O6	.675					.729		.617
AC2							.779	.689
AC1	.650						.767	.739
eigen value	3.310	2.706	2.404	2.267	1.658	1.589		
% of variance	14.392	11.765	10.453	9.858	7.210	6.909		
Cummulative %	14.392	26.157	36.610	46.468	53.679	60.588		

Note: PL = Participative Leadership; FT = Fair Treatment; TE= Team Effectiveness; JI= Job Involvement; O= Opportunity

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

3.3. Heteroscedasticity consistent standard error

An alternative and highly appealing method of reducing the effects of heteroscedasticity on inference is to employ a heteroscedasticity-consistent standard error (HCSE) estimator of OLS parameter estimates. To illustrate the application of an HC estimator, we analyze a data set using OLS regression, first estimating the standard errors of the regression coefficients using OLSE, and then using HC3.

Figure-1

Figure-2

As there was some normality found but homoscedasticity was not found so heteroscedasticity Rlm was estimated as suggested by (Hayes, 2017) heteroscedasticity consistent standard error estimator is being.

The value of the coefficient beta usually improves the relationship between the predictor (independent with dependent Variable). The results tell us that the beta of all predictor variables i.e. team effectiveness, opportunity, affective commitment, job involvement fair treatment have a positive relationship with participative leadership. Furthermore, in this table, the significance value had shown the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable. When the value of the T statistic is more than 1.96 at a 95% confidence interval so this means there is a significant impact & if the value is less than 1.96 will result in an insignificant impact. As well as significant value must be less than 0.05. As per the result job involvement has less than criteria 0.724 which means insignificant effect and opportunity shows 1.962 which is higher than the criteria but the significant value is higher than the 0.05 and lower bound and upper bound signs do not match so it is also insignificant whereas the others (team effectiveness, affective commitment, fair treatment had a significant impact on Participative Leadership. The value of R square tells us the independent variable predicts 24% variance on dependent & F stats 16.472 shows overall as well as the combined effect of independent variable if it is existing or not.

Table: 4. 6
 Regression Analysis: With Heteroscedasticity-Consistent Standard Error
 Using RLM (2017) Macro

Hypothesis	Predictors	Estimates			Confidence Interval at 95%			Remarks	
		Unstandardized	HCSE	Standardized	T-value	Sig	Lower Bound		Upper Bound
	Constant	0.692	2.116		0.327	0.744	-3.482	4.800	
H1	Team Effectiveness	0.348	0.157	0.172	2.220	0.028	0.039	0.658	Supported
H2	Affective Commitment	0.571	0.276	0.220	2.068	0.040	0.026	1.115	Supported
H3	Opportunities	0.452	0.230	0.180	1.962	0.051	-0.002	0.906	Not Supported
H4	Fair Treatment	0.246	0.093	0.177	2.633	0.009	0.062	0.430	Supported
H5	Job Involvement	0.075	0.103	0.054	0.724	0.470	-0.129	0.279	Not Supported

Notes: HCSE = Heteroscedasticity-Consistent Standard Error

Dependent Variable = Participative Leadership

Adjusted R-square = 0.240

F statistic (5, 195) = 16.472 (p < .001)

4. Discussion

The results have shown that team effectiveness, affective commitment, & fair treatment supported the hypothesis by showing significant value whereas the job involvement and opportunity didn't support by showing less than 1.96 criteria and having an insignificant impact on participative leadership. Whereas in opportunity the t statistic value is greater than the criteria of it but the significance value shows an insignificant effect of 0.051 as well as their lower and upper bound interval is showing different signs and having an insignificant impact on participative leadership. The first hypothesis resulted that team effectiveness has a significant relationship with participative leadership. It is key to the enhanced accomplishment of team goals & greater effectiveness by increasing the use of effective teams in the organization, & highlighting the importance of the participative decision-making process (Choi et al., 2017). Affective commitment has a significant relation with participative leadership. Commitment is the level of loyalty or emotional involvement with the firm success. Here, loyalty is the responsibility (participating in the decision-making) given to the employee which impacts the goal achievement of the organization. With this feeling, employees feel important in the organization (Luthan, 2006).

According to (Roberson, 2006) whenever the organization gives a task to the employee it increases the opportunity to learn and helps in the decision-making process the more employee gets opportunities the more he learns, which improves the creativity of the worker while making a decision but if there is a lack of skills in an employee, he/she cannot avail the opportunity. There is an insignificant relationship between opportunity & Participative Leadership. Fairness in the organization gives employees importance in the firm. He feels respect at the workplace, this style of leadership always gives justice to the employee for performing well in the company. Fair treatment is very important in the organization with this workers will be satisfied and biases will be reduced. It also gives fairness in participation in decision-making (Ghaffari et al., 2017). Hence fair treatment has a significant relation with participative leadership. If an employee doesn't have good skill so, he/she become de-motivated, and level of self-confidence decrease. A leader has high expectations of their worker but sometimes employees failed to fulfill their expectations. Because employee thinks that low involvement in the decision-making is just because of skill it may be the creativity or any other skills which reflect the job involvement of worker and decision-making of the firm. Employees just need proper guidelines for achieving their tasks. The higher expectation with guidelines makes employee motivated for their work. The psychological factor is considered to be the reason for low job involvement Job involvement has an insignificant impact on the Participative Leadership

5. Recommendation and Future Research

Manufacturing organization has to evaluate their managerial leadership for making their workers more effective as well as productive (Awais et al., 2017). The concept of participative leadership is generated through path-goal theory. There are two sets of behavior that managers shall use for managing the team (House, 1996). Some of the studies have analyzed the antecedent of it. This leadership will increase the level of creativity but will not enhance the team's efficiency. It perform a different function with the team outcome which is team proficiency (Martin et al., 2013). In the manufacturing sector leaders should be careful to manage effectively while talking with the employee. Participative leadership interacts with their followers about their leadership. This style increases the affective commitment & will impact organizational development. The importance of followers must be highlighted for

achieving a better understanding with this it does enhance the interaction among them. If employees think, he is being treated fairly will automatically increase their satisfaction level. (Rogiest et al., 2018). In Pakistani society where ideas sharing from employees have not been encouraged. Every manager wants creativity in the work of their subordinates. Creativity is included in the efficiency of the team (Fatima, Safdar, & Jahanzeb, 2017). Leaders shall improve team efficiency by telling what to do and how to complete tasks (Li et al., 2018). Efficiency is said to be an important dimension of team performance. Affective commitment increases the job performance of employees because if a worker is loyal to the organization his performance level increases and he/ she will improve day by day. Leadership itself makes a culture in the firm so that workers commit to the service they delivered (Bell & Mjoli, 2013). They should pay attention to high job performance as organizational career growth because its leads to commitment (Wang et al., 2017). In this research, there are five predictors including (Team effectiveness, Affective Commitment, Opportunity, Fair treatment, and last but not least Job involvement to check the impact on participative leadership in the manufacturing & industrial sector. Other predictors shall be considered for future research such as Creativity, Job Satisfaction. As this research is totally based on direct impact “Motivation” as a mediator shall be included in the study for the future direction.

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